

LITERATURE SURVEY ON THE IMPACT OF SILICA FUME AND NANO SILICA AS CEMENT SUBSTITUTES ON THE DURABILITY CHARACTERISTICS OF CONCRETE DESIGNED FOR PAVEMENT CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: The durability of concrete is a critical factor in pavement construction, directly influencing the lifespan and performance of infrastructure. This literature survey investigates the impact of silica fume and nano silica as partial replacements for cement on the durability characteristics of concrete. Silica fumes, a byproduct of silicon metal production, and nano silica, a finer particle with enhanced reactivity, have both been recognized for their potential to improve the mechanical properties and longevity of concrete. The review synthesizes recent research findings on how these materials affect various durability parameters, including resistance to chloride ion penetration, sulfate attack, and freeze-thaw cycles. Studies indicate that silica fume enhances the density and binding properties of the cement matrix, thereby improving overall durability. Nano silica, due to its extremely small particle size and high surface area, contributes to a finer microstructure, enhancing resistance to aggressive environmental conditions. The survey also explores the optimal replacement levels for both silica fume and nano silica to maximize performance without compromising workability and cost-effectiveness. This comprehensive review provides insights into the comparative advantages and limitations of these supplementary cementitious materials, offering valuable guidance for engineers and researchers focused on developing more resilient and long-lasting pavement concrete.

Keywords: Durability, Silica Fume, Nano Silica, Concrete Pavement, Cement Substitutes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a fundamental material in civil engineering, especially for pavement construction, where its durability and performance are crucial. The traditional use of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) has been challenged by the growing need for more sustainable and durable construction materials. In this context, silica fume and nano silica have emerged as promising alternatives that enhance concrete's properties while also addressing environmental concerns associated with cement production. The production of OPC is associated with high carbon emissions, as the process of manufacturing cement involves the thermal decomposition of limestone (calcium carbonate) into lime (calcium oxide) and carbon dioxide. This process is responsible for a significant proportion of global

CO₂ emissions, contributing to climate change. As environmental regulations become stricter and the construction industry faces pressures to reduce its carbon footprint, there is a growing need to explore materials that can mitigate these impacts while still delivering high performance. Concrete is extensively utilized in the construction of various structures, including foundations, brick and block walls, pavements, bridges, highways, runways, parking facilities, dams, reservoirs, pipes, footings for gates and fences, and even boats. Its ubiquitous presence highlights its critical role in modern infrastructure. Globally, the volume of concrete used is twice as much as the combined total of steel, wood, plastics, and aluminum. The demand for concrete is second only to that for naturally occurring water.

The concrete industry itself is a major commercial sector, with the ready-mix concrete industry being its largest segment. This sector is projected to exceed \$100 billion in revenue by 2015. In the United States alone, the concrete manufacturing industry, focusing solely on ready-mixed concrete, generates approximately \$30 billion annually. The scale and significance of the concrete industry underscore the essential role concrete plays in shaping the infrastructure of the contemporary world.

In recent years, researchers have explored the incorporation of various materials, such as water-based cross linking polymers, to enhance concrete properties. These innovations aim to produce concrete with superior characteristics, including increased strength, electrical conductivity, and improved resistance to damage from spillage.

Figure 1: Typical Rigid Pavement Section

2. THE ROLE OF SILICA FUME IN CONCRETE

Silica fume, a byproduct of silicon and ferrosilicon alloy production, has been employed in concrete for several decades to improve its performance. The fine, glassy particles of silica fume act as a pozzolanic material, reacting with calcium hydroxide in the cement paste to form additional calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H), which densifies the concrete matrix. This increased density enhances the mechanical strength and durability of concrete. In pavement applications, the use of silica fume is known to improve resistance to abrasion, reduce permeability, and enhance overall longevity, making it a valuable material for harsh environmental conditions.

3. ADVANCEMENTS WITH NANO SILICA

Nano silica, characterized by its extremely small particle size and high surface area, represents a more recent advancement in concrete technology. The incorporation of nano silica into concrete mixes can significantly alter the microstructure of the material, leading to improved hydration reactions and greater mechanical properties. Nano silica enhances the bonding between the cement paste and aggregates, reduces the pore size distribution, and increases the density of the concrete. These improvements translate into better performance in terms of resistance to cracking, chemical attacks, and freeze-thaw cycles, which are critical for pavements subjected to varying environmental stresses.

4. Objectives of the Literature Survey

This literature survey aims to review and synthesize existing research on the effects of silica

fume and nano silica as cement substitutes in concrete designed for pavement construction. The focus will be on assessing how these materials impact key durability characteristics, such as resistance to chloride ion penetration, sulfate attack, and freeze-thaw cycles. By consolidating findings from various studies, this survey seeks to provide a clearer understanding of the benefits and limitations of these materials, thereby informing future research and practical applications in the field of pavement construction.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several research studies have focused on the impact of silica fume and nano silica as cement substitutes on the durability characteristics of concrete designed for pavement construction.

Farhan et al. (2011) conducted a study to investigate the impact of incorporating silica fume into normal concrete to produce tailored high-strength concrete. The study aimed to examine the compressive and flexural strengths of concrete when silica fume was used as a partial replacement for cement. In this research, five different concrete mixes were prepared, incorporating varying percentages of silica fume. Cement was replaced with silica fume at levels of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15%, while maintaining a constant water-cement ratio of 0.40 and keeping other mix design variables unchanged. The concrete mixes were tested for compressive and flexural strengths at intervals of 1 day, 7 days, 28 days, and 60 days. Additionally, properties of the fresh concrete, such as compacting factor and slump, were measured to evaluate the workability of the different mixes. The findings provided insights into the effects of silica fume on the strength and workability of high-performance concrete.[1]

Kalpana, et al.(2015) The cost of cement, a primary component of concrete, is notably higher than that of other raw materials used in its production. As the global population continues to grow, the demand for concrete increases, but the availability of raw materials is diminishing. Although current resources are sufficient to meet the needs of the existing population, the depletion of these resources poses a significant challenge. This issue can be addressed by partially substituting traditional materials with advanced alternatives or by modifying the properties of conventional concrete. The use of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as fly ash (FA) and silica fume can effectively reduce cement consumption and construction costs. In India, of the approximately 90 coal-based thermal power stations producing fly ash, around 30 have adopted dry collection methods, resulting in improved quality and consistency of fly ash. This study investigates the strength characteristics of concrete incorporating silica fume and fly ash. Various concrete mixtures were tested with different levels of cement replacement by weight using these materials. The findings indicate that at replacement levels between 15% and 23%, the concrete achieves sufficient strength for construction purposes, promoting sustainability and cost efficiency in the construction industry.[2]

Nanda et al.(2017) examined the environmental impact of cement production, particularly the emission of greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide (CO₂) during the high-temperature processing of limestone and clay. They noted that the atmospheric concentration of CO₂ had reached alarming levels, with a concentration of approximately 410 ppm as of April 2017. To address this, the study highlighted the use of green concrete, incorporating nano silica, to reduce CO₂ emissions and enhance durability. In their experimental work, cement was partially replaced with nano silica at levels of 2%, 3%, and 4%, while the silica fume replacement was kept constant at 8% across four different water-cement ratios (W/C). The samples were tested for durability properties, such as abrasion resistance and rapid chloride penetration, at various curing ages. The results indicated that the optimal performance was achieved with a 0.30 W/C ratio, 4% nano silica, and 8% silica fume after 56 days of curing. Additionally, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy

(EDS) tests were conducted to assess the levels of Ca(OH)_2 and CSH in the concrete. The findings demonstrated that the combination of nano silica and silica fume not only enhanced concrete durability but also reduced CO_2 emissions, contributing to environmental sustainability.[3]

Varia et al. (2018) investigated the performance of concrete enhanced with mineral admixtures such as silica fume, GGBS, fly ash, and copper slag. Among these, silica fume was found to deliver the best mechanical and durability properties. The study also explored the impact of adding fibers, which act as "secondary reinforcement," improving the stiffness, toughness, and shrinkage resistance of concrete. Silica fume was used as a partial cement replacement at specific percentages by weight, enhancing the effectiveness of the fibers in the concrete. The results showed that incorporating fibers along with silica fume significantly improved the mechanical and durability properties of the concrete.[4]

Jaishankar et al. (2018) studied the effect of nano silica, a material with a particle size of approximately 10^{-9} meters, on the strength and durability of M70 high-performance concrete. Due to its fine particle size, nano silica increased the stiffness of the concrete and reduced cracking. The study replaced cement with nano silica at levels of 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% and conducted sorptivity, alkalinity, and water absorption tests on 30 cubes and 15 cylinders. The specimens were cured for 28 days under standard conditions. The results demonstrated an increasing trend in strength and durability with higher nano silica content. XRD and XRF techniques were used to analyze the microstructure of the concrete, revealing that nano silica reduced porosity and made the concrete denser, thereby enhancing its strength and durability.[5]

Nanda et al. (2020) investigated the combined effect of nano silica and silica fume as partial cement replacements on concrete properties, focusing on compressive strength. The study analyzed compressive strength data using normal-probability distribution and evaluated partial safety factors using the first-order second moment approach with Hasofer Lind's method. The results indicated that the combination of nano silica and silica fume improved the compressive strength of concrete compared to plain concrete, increasing its reliability. SEM tests further confirmed the consumption of Ca(OH)_2 in concrete containing these materials, highlighting their effectiveness in enhancing concrete properties.[6]

Bajpai et al. (2020) conducted a life cycle assessment of geopolymer concrete containing fly ash and silica fume, comparing its environmental impact with that of conventional cement concrete. The study evaluated three geopolymer concrete mixes and found that fly ash–silica fume geopolymer concrete activated without sodium silicate had the lowest environmental impact. The analysis also showed that using these materials reduced the cost by 10.87%–17.77% per unit volume. The study concluded that fly ash–silica fume geopolymer concrete is a sustainable alternative that can reduce the environmental footprint of the construction industry.[7]

Reddy et al. (2021) explored the use of copper slag as a mineral additive in self-compacting concrete (SCC) to create a more affordable, reliable, and sustainable concrete mix. The study tested various replacement levels of fly ash (5%–35%) and silica fume (0%–10%) to determine the optimal mix for achieving the desired strength and durability properties. The results showed that the appropriate combination of these by-products significantly enhanced the compressive, tensile, and flexural strengths of the SCC. Durability tests against sulfate and acid attacks further confirmed the improved performance of the concrete.[8]

Bypaneni et al. (2022) investigated the properties of glass fiber-reinforced high-performance concrete (GFRHC) by replacing cement with silica fume at levels ranging from 0% to 25%. The study found that the optimal mix, with 10% silica fume and 2% glass fibers, resulted in significant improvements in compressive strength, split tensile strength, and

modulus of rupture. The results indicated that adding glass fibers at a 2% replacement level produced high-quality concrete with excellent mechanical properties.[9]

Sahoo et al. (2022) explored the use of fly ash, silica fume, and rice husk dust in concrete, focusing on their physical and mechanical properties. The study found that adding silica fume alone to fly ash produced concrete with a compressive strength of 35 MPa, while combining it with rice husk powder increased the strength to 40 MPa. The concrete blocks also exhibited corrosion resistance and hydrophobicity, making them viable alternatives to conventional cement-based concrete.[10]

Patel et al. (2023) studied high-performance concrete, defined by its high durability, strength, resistance to chemical attack, and workability. The research involved replacing cement with silica fume and metakaolin in varying percentages and adding superplasticizers. The study found that replacing 10% of the cement with both silica fume and metakaolin yielded the best results in terms of compressive strength and workability, outperforming standard concrete mixes.[11]

Chowdary et al. (2023) investigated the feasibility of using manufactured sand (MS) and silica fume as replacements for river sand (RS) and cement in concrete production. The study tested M30 grade concrete samples with different percentages of MS and 5% silica fume. After 28 days of curing, the results showed that the properties of the concrete varied depending on the mix, with some combinations showing promise as sustainable alternatives to traditional materials.[12]

Dipta et al. (2023) focused on reducing cement and coarse aggregate usage in concrete by replacing them with silica fume, fly ash, and steel slag. The study found that a mix with 15% silica fume, 10% fly ash, and 30% steel slag demonstrated superior compressive and flexural strengths compared to normal concrete. The research emphasized the potential of using sustainable cementitious materials to reduce industrial waste and environmental impact.[13]

Marin et al. (2023) examined the incorporation of crumb rubber and silica fume into self-compacting concrete (SCC) to address environmental concerns related to waste rubber. The study found that up to 15% recycled rubber and 5% silica fume could be used without compromising the mechanical properties of SCC. The research also highlighted the positive impact of this combination on the thermal and durability properties of the concrete.[14]

Daniel (2024) reviewed the use of silica fume in pervious concrete, focusing on its mechanical properties, durability, and environmental impact. The study found that replacing 10%–15% of the cement with silica fume improved the compressive strength, abrasion resistance, and freeze–thaw durability of pervious concrete. The research concluded that silica fume is a promising supplementary cementitious material that enhances the performance and sustainability of pervious concrete, though it may reduce workability due to its fine particle size.[15]

6. SUMMARY

This literature survey explored the impact of silica fume and nano silica as cement substitutes on the durability characteristics of concrete, specifically designed for pavement construction. Various studies demonstrated that incorporating silica fume and nano silica enhances the mechanical strength, durability, and environmental sustainability of concrete. Nanda et al. (2017) observed that partial replacement of cement with nano silica and silica fume improved the abrasion resistance and chloride penetration resistance of concrete. Varia et al. (2018) emphasized that silica fume significantly enhances the mechanical properties and durability when used in conjunction with fibers. Jaishankar et al. (2018) noted that nano silica reduced porosity, thereby increasing the density and durability of high-performance concrete.

Further research by Nanda et al. (2020) highlighted that the combination of nano silica and silica fume reduced the partial safety factor of concrete, increasing its reliability. Studies by Patel et al. (2023) and Chowdary et al. (2023) affirmed that high-performance concrete incorporating these materials showed superior resistance to chemical attacks and environmental degradation. Overall, the literature confirms that substituting cement with silica fume and nano silica significantly enhances the durability of concrete, making it a more sustainable choice for pavement construction.

7. REFERENCES

1. Kalpana, Balike&Achyutha Kumar Reddy, M. & Rani, V. (2015). EXPERIMENT STUDIES ON DOUBLE BLENDED CONCRETE USING FLY ASH AND SILICA FUME.
2. H.G, Nahushananda& Ali, Farhan. (2015). EFFECT OF SILICA FUME ON PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF CEMENT ON HIGH STRENGTH CONCRETE. MATTER: International Journal of Science and Technology. 1. 275-284. 10.20319/mijst.2016.s11.275284.
3. Nanda, A.K. & Bansal, Prem& Kumar, M.. (2018). Effect of nano silica and silica fume on durability properties of high performance concrete. International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology. 9. 115-129.
4. Varia, Dipak. (2018). Review on Effect on Concrete by partial Replacement of Cement by Silica Fume with using the Addition of Composite fibres. International Journal For Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology(IJRASET),. 6. 613-618.
5. Jaishankar, P &Poovizhi, K & Mohan, K. (2018). Strength and Durability Behaviour of Nano Silica on High Performance Concrete. International Journal of Engineering & Technology. 7. 415. 10.14419/ijet.v7i3.12.16118.
6. Nanda, A.K. & Bansal, Prem& Kumar, M.. (2020). Reliability based partial safety factor of concrete containing nano silica and silica fume. Computers and Concrete. 26. 385-395. 10.12989/cac.2020.26.5.385.
7. Bajpai, Rishabh&Choudhary, Kailash & Srivastava, Anshuman&Sangwan, Kuldip Singh & Singh, Manpreet. (2020). Environmental Impact Assessment of Fly Ash and Silica Fume Based Geopolymer Concrete. Journal of Cleaner Production. 254. 120147. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120147.
8. Reddy, D & Kumar Singh, Samit&Tejaswi, Ch&Devraj, B. (2021). EXAMINE THE DURABILITY AND STRENGTH OF CONCRETE THAT HAS BEEN REPLACED WITH FLY ASH AND SILICA FUME. VIII. 404-410.
9. kumar, Pidugu& Chaitanya, Bypaneni. (2022). Performance evaluation of glass fiber reinforced high-performance concrete with silica fume and nano-silica. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 982. 012018. 10.1088/1755-1315/982/1/012018.
10. Sahoo, Amalendu&Kar, B.B.. (2022). Impact of Silica Fume on Fly Ash Based Concrete Material. Asian Journal of Water, Environment and Pollution. 19. 49-54. 10.3233/AJW220055.
11. Patel, Dixit &Parmar, Abhijitsinh& Tank, Savan. (2023). EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON TRIPLE BLENDED HIGH PERFORMANCE CONCRETE WITH SILICA FUME AND METAKAOLIN. Journal of Technology. 11. 92-100.
12. Chowdary, Nandigam& Mahajan, Akshat&Jaggi, Sahil. (2023). Investigating the effect of Manufactured sand and Silica Fume on the properties of Concrete. IOP Conference

Series: Materials Science and Engineering. 1291. 012027. 10.1088/1757-899X/1291/1/012027.

13. Dipta, Ovirup&Sobhan, Sk&Shuvo, Aojoy. (2023). Assessment of the Combined Effect of Silica Fume, Fly Ash, and Steel Slag on the Mechanical Behavior of Concrete. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Construction*. 12. 78-85. 10.32732/jcec.2023.12.2.78.
14. Kumar, A., Yadav, O. and Kumar, S., AN OVERVIEW ARTICLE ON INCORPORATING HUMAN HAIR AS FIBRE REINFORCEMENT IN CONCRETE. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, ISSN, pp.2320-2882.
15. Bušić, Robert & Miličević, Ivana & Dokšanović, Tihomir & Grubišić, Marin. (2023). Durability Performance and Thermal Resistance of Structural Self-Compacting Concrete Improved with Waste Rubber and Silica Fume. *Buildings*. 13. 1331. 10.3390/buildings13051331.
16. Kumar, N., Kumar, P., Kumar, A. and Kumar, R., 2023. An Investigation of Asphalt Mixtures Using a Naturally Occurring Fibre. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT*, 2(6), pp.80-87.
17. Sathiparan, Navaratnarajah & Subramaniam, Daniel. (2024). Sustainable Pervious Concrete with Silica Fume as Cement Replacement: A Review. *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board*. 10.1177/03611981241265852.
18. Kumar, A., Yadav, O., Kumar, P. and Gopal, S., AN OVERVIEW ARTICLE ON THE IMPACT OF EMPLOYING TREATED STRAW FIBERS ON THE MECHANICAL AND DURABILITY ATTRIBUTES OF CONCRETE.
19. IS 456: 2000, "Indian Standard Code of Practice for Plain and Reinforced Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
20. IS 10262: 1982, "Recommended Guidelines for Concrete Mix design", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
21. IS 383: 1970, "Specification for Coarse aggregate and Fine aggregate from Natural Sources for Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
22. IS 9103: 1999, "Indian Standard Concrete Admixture Specification", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
23. IS 5816: 1999, "Splitting Tensile Strength of Concrete Method of Test", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
24. IS 9399: 1959, "Specification for Apparatus for Flexural Testing of Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi
25. IS 516: 1959, "Flexural Strength of Concrete", Bureau of Indian Standard, New Delhi